

D6.10: Final Interoperability Testbed Report

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Abstract:

This document provides the final status of the interoperability testbeds, the activities undertaken and the services deployed, together with the description of the results achieved. It contains the final recommendations regarding the challenges encountered, with particular focus on the interoperability aspects. The recommendations are based on the experiences of the pilot testbeds used by the Science Demonstrators, along with those of the Data Interoperability demonstrators and associated research e-infrastructures.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In the context of the EOSCpilot project, the aim of the Interoperability Work Package (WP6) was to develop and demonstrate the interoperability requirements between e-Infrastructures, domain research infrastructures and other service providers needed in the European Open Science Cloud. It dealt with interoperability in general leading to the ability to "plug and play" the services of the EOSC in the future. While the goal of the *Science Demonstrators* (WP4) was to show how some particular services can work together, there was also a need to work on a more general framework for interoperability between data and services. WP6 worked closely with WP4 (Science Demonstrators) and WP5 (Services), taking inputs from the Science Demonstrators to ensure the relevance of the interoperability framework, and from the Services.

The interoperability was mapped in two tracks:

- Research and Data Interoperability:
 - The Research and Data Interoperability Track – that provides the research infrastructure and domain expert view in the work-programme with focus on data interoperability. The definition of a Data Interoperability framework in EOSC is based on the FAIR principles - data and services need to be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.
- Infrastructure Interoperability:
 - The complementary usage of Cloud, Grid, HTC and HPC infrastructures, including large datastores, through high speed networks and performant data transfer protocols and tools. The high-level objective is to facilitate the most adequate infrastructures for the treatment of extensive amounts of data, generated by new generations of instruments, observatories, satellites, sensors, sequencers, imaging facilities and numerical simulations, and produced by well-known data intensive communities but also by the long tail of science.
 - In the Infrastructure Interoperability track the provider view is in the center of the work programme.
 - The federated infrastructure pilots that have to be set up with the resources provided by other partners involved in this WP and by the selected Science Demonstrators will enable the analyses of the existing interoperation mechanisms for software components, services, workflows, users and resource access within existing RI systems.

The objective of this deliverable is to present the final status of the various testbeds, assessment of the interoperability of the various solutions and services used and/or implemented, and the final requirements collected from all the Science Demonstrators and other use cases that were object of the WP6 activities.

1. INTRODUCTION

The EOSCpilot project has been funded to support the first phase in the development of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). One of the three main objectives of the project was to develop a number of demonstrators functioning as high-profile pilots that integrate services and infrastructures to show interoperability and its benefits. The pilots were in a number of scientific domains such as Earth Sciences, High-Energy Physics, Social Sciences, Life Sciences, Physics and Astronomy. These activities leveraged already existing resources and capabilities from different research infrastructure and e-infrastructure organizations, to maximize their use across the research community.

In the context of the project the Interoperability Work Package, WP6, has specific objectives that are guiding the activity of task T6.3 - Interoperability pilots (service implementation, integration, validation, provisioning for Science Demonstrators):

- Providing the architecture, validated technical solutions and best practices for enabling interoperability across multiple federated e-infrastructures, overcoming current gaps expressed by user communities and resource providers.
- Validating the compliance of services provided by WP5 with specifications and requirements defined by the Science Demonstrators in WP4.
- Defining and setting up distributed Interoperability Pilots, involving multiple infrastructures, providers and scientific communities, with the purpose of validating the WP5 service portfolio.
- Assessing the maturity level of solutions in close cooperation with the Science Demonstrators, taking into account factors such as technology readiness level, openness, scalability, user community adoption and sustainability.

This document provides the final status of the interoperability testbeds, the activities done and the services deployed, together with the description of the results achieved, as commented by the players involved in the project activity: Science Demonstrators, Data Interoperability demonstrators and research e-infrastructures.

After the collection of the initial requirements on the interoperability testbeds, reported in D6.4¹, the activity continued on supporting the projects Science Demonstrators and an interim report on the status of the testbeds was provided in deliverable D6.5². In the second part of the project after first round of selected Science Demonstrators were almost at the end of their activities, and while the second round was at the beginning, an updated list of requirements regarding interoperability aspects was provided in the deliverable D6.7³. We are closing our activities with this final report (D6.10).

The document follows the same structure of the previous deliverables, with two main sections. The first section deals with *Interoperability in the EOSC context*, with subsections delving into the interoperability requirements and aspects at both the e-infrastructure and data research e-infrastructures levels. The second section considers the Science Demonstrators, with three subsections grouping the demonstrators by their phase within the project.

The document closes with the outcome of the activity to assess the interoperability potential of the various software solutions used/improved/developed by the Science Demonstrators during the lifetime of the EOSCpilot project. This activity was based on the *Interoperability Quick Assessment Toolkit (IQAT@)*⁴, developed by the ISA² programme, Action 2016.33⁵, “Assessment of trans-European systems supporting EU policies of the Interoperability solutions and common frameworks”. In particular, we used the

¹ [D6.4: Initial Requirements of the Interoperability Testbeds](#)

² [D6.5: Interim Interoperability Testbed report](#)

³ [D6.7: Revised Requirements of the Interoperability Testbeds](#)

⁴ <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/solution/interoperability-quick-assessment-toolkit/about>

⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/actions/evaluating-and-rationalising-ict-public-administrations_en

*Interoperability Quick Assessment Excel Tool*⁶, an Excel tool used to calculate solutions interoperability maturity, and the *Guidelines for Solution Owners*⁷, a short document that includes the **methodology** that describes the high-level steps to be followed by *Solution Owners* for assessing the potential interoperability of a solution.

The Interoperability Quick Assessment Toolkit, developed in the context of Action 2.1 of the Interoperability Solutions for European Public Administrations (ISA) Programme, is based on the **Conceptual Model for the Interoperability Quick Assessment of software solutions** presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model for the IQA

This Interoperability Conceptual Model comprises the following four Interoperability Areas to be assessed through the toolkit:

- **IOP Governance:** assesses the overall governance of Interoperability. It assesses factors relevant to actions that took place before the actual development of the system. It also includes factors relevant to the existence of policies and processes to safeguard interoperability.
- **Software Architecture:** assesses the maturity of the internal software architecture of a solution as well as the coordination of interactions with other software solutions, based on the EIRA model².
- **Human to Machine (H2M) Interface:** assesses the interaction, including semantic aspects, between a solution and its human end-users.
- **Machine to Machine (M2M) Interface:** assesses the interaction, including semantic aspects, between a solution and other software solutions

The scores obtained for the software solutions used in EOSCpilot are just a first attempt in the direction of interoperability assessment and should be read with care, as the services evaluated are mainly for the scientific research environment and do not always match the characteristics of the of solutions developed for public administration.

A copy of the Interoperability Quick Assessment Tool is presented in Annex 2.

⁶ https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/rdf_entity/http_e_f_data_ceuropa_ceu_fw21_f234ba476_b2523_b4c6b_b9d76_b4f04b9f6c36d

⁷ <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/solution/interoperability-quick-assessment-toolkit/distribution/guidelines-solution-owners-v110>

2. INTEROPERABILITY IN THE EOSC CONTEXT

The success of the EOSC relies strongly on the ability to interconnect data and infrastructures on the European level, because these will be the backbone behind the services offered to the research community. For the interoperability of data the usefulness of the FAIR principle is widely accepted, though open access by-default is far from being in place in all relevant communities. The aim of the EOSCpilot was to point out critical aspects in this context and to highlight solutions to put the FAIR principle at work. The EOSC aims to offer 1.7 million European researchers and 70 million professionals in science, technology, the humanities and social sciences, a virtual environment with open and seamless services for storage, management, analysis and re-use of research data, across borders and scientific disciplines, by federating existing scientific data infrastructures, currently dispersed across disciplines and the EU Member States.

Considering the recommendations of the Commission 2nd High Level Expert Group⁸ on the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), 2018, we can clearly see how interoperability remains an important objective to be followed, from the description of the intention of EOSC to *'interlink people, data, services and training, publications, projects and organisations across borders and scientific disciplines'*. In order to meet this goal one of the first actions to be done is to ***'select standards and community-endorsed best practices to ensure interoperability and composability of EOSC services and resources (separate for all elements of the ecosystem – data, data access services, software, etc. – but with a systemic perspective to develop a trustable ecosystem), and promote and enforce their adoption across research communities, leveraging existing international initiatives and collaborations'***.

Also, an aim of the EOSC Portal, the web-portal that provides access to data, services and resources, is to *'promote the development of services as independent, interoperable and exchangeable building blocks to foster the future accreditation of innovative and/or efficient alternatives, connected and built upon a base of well-defined and stable core services, notably in areas that are science-agnostic and provide an opportunity to use common solutions to access, manage and process big data'*.

At the end of the EOSCpilot project many of the services and solutions proposed to or developed by the Science Demonstrators, based on the results achieved and the quality of the services proposed, find themselves meeting the criteria needed in order to be included in the EOSC Portal Marketplace or be part of EOSC-Hub Thematic Services.

2.1. E-Infrastructure Interoperability

In the Infrastructure Interoperability track, represented by T6.1, the 'provider' view was the center of the work-programme.

The "e-Infrastructure Gap Analysis" deliverable (D6.1)⁹ - identified the main reasons that prevent exploitation and usage of existing e-infrastructures and distributed resources and concerning their inter-connection. It also gave axes to build bridges regarding the identified gaps.

It was followed by the "EOSC architecture design and validation procedure" deliverable (D6.2)¹⁰ – that proposed and validated technical solutions and suggested best practices for enabling interoperability across multiple federated e-infrastructures.

The "Final EOSC Architecture" deliverable (D6.8)¹¹ - refines the architectural design for the interoperation of various types of infrastructures, initially proposed in deliverable D6.2, which could participate to the future EOSC. From the point of view of this deliverable, one of the important aspects presented in D6.8 is the description of the technical and policy aspects regarding how to ensure the e-infrastructure interoperability,

⁸ https://www.eosc-portal.eu/sites/default/files/KI0318339ENN.en_.pdf

⁹ <https://www.eoscpilot.eu/content/d61-e-infrastructure-gap-analysis>

¹⁰ <https://www.eoscpilot.eu/content/d62-eosc-architecture-design-and-validation-procedure>

¹¹ <https://www.eoscpilot.eu/content/d68-final-eosc-architecture>

together with the description of how to verify the e-infrastructure interoperability. D6.8 presents the interoperability verification checklists, summarizing the internal verifications, that can be done by the local infrastructure management, and external assessment of the infrastructure by other entities in the EOSC.

2.1.1. Pilot for Connecting Computing Centers

Many initiatives exist at European level in EOSC to federate several computing and/or storage infrastructures for data, and for data analysis to flow between those infrastructures. This is mainly organized for the benefit of scientific communities, like High Energy Physics, Bioinformatics or Climate change, to cite but a few. Many developments exist as well to make computation accessible to a much wider range of scientific communities, by the deployment of user-friendly interfaces or tools like Galaxy server, containerization, clusters in the cloud, at Tier 3 level.

This leaves Tier 2 and Tier 1 infrastructures “orphan” in the building of those networks connecting data storage and computation. Therefore, PiCO2 was proposed at a meeting of WP6 (Amsterdam, 20-21 February 2017) as one of the first interoperability pilots to provide some tools for facilitating the flow of data and codes for computation between Tier 2 and Tier 1 infrastructures. Most of the national systems, such as in France, have deployed a pyramidal organization, with several Tier 1 infrastructures (e.g. IDRIS, CCIN2P3, etc) that are each possibly connected to some Tier 2 infrastructures (so called “Mésocenters”) by file transfers.

The objective of PiCO2 is to promote the possibility of data and codes flow along the edges of a network, between data centers (data storage and computation, Tier 1 and Tier 2), which are agnostic as far as a thematic application is concerned, i.e. which can serve an as-large-as-is-possible diversity of scientific communities.

Sites involved

Most of the sites involved are currently located in France. Current participants are:

- French National centers: IDRIS, Orsay, CNRS and CC IN2P3, Lyon, CNRS.
- French National Grid Initiative (France-Grille) and GRIF, CEA, Orsay.
- Network: RENATER.
- Mesocenters (Tiers 2): GRICAD, CNRS & Université de Grenoble-Alpes, Grenoble and MClA, Université de Bordeaux.
- INRA/INRIA, Bordeaux, for testbeds, data and programs.
- Some connections have been established with DESY, Hamburg, Germany.

Additionally, a study on using AARC2 recommendations was undertaken in conjunction with the UK’s IRIS consortium by STFC at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory.

IRODS zones federation

Access to data across different level HPC clusters is crucial to allow scientists to scale-out the testing of hypotheses developed in the laboratory. Traditional transfer methods, such as physical supports exchange, ftp or scp, are often prone to shortcomings and will be increasingly so. They can be cumbersome, slow, insecure, complex to set up and operate, and even a source of error. Seamless access to data from all computational platforms is therefore a desirable goal. The PiCO2 project has tested a promising approach to **leverage the federation capability** offered by the **iRODS** open source data management system, present within many mesocenters and research institutions, in order to offer this capability. Different points were discussed and implemented:

- Create a group of experts to coordinate and exchange on the operations to setup federations between iRODS zones.
- Carry out POC federations between pilot sites.
- Assess the impact, performance and adoption of the set-up federations.

The main lessons learned from this work are that the **construction of a federation** between iRODS zones technically requires a **high level of investment** and is very **complex** (especially with iRODS V3). A federation is a federation that is built "peer-to-peer", between two zones. If there are n zones, it is therefore necessary to build all n^2 federations between two zones. This is possible for some areas, more difficult for further development between a significant number of zones.

The main findings are that the iRODS technology can be a limit in order to connect distributed storage over some infrastructures. Other technologies have still to be tested.

Network requirement for Pico2

Since cloud infrastructures and users are distributed all over Europe, network connectivity between them is therefore a pillar on which EOSC has to be built. The stability, robustness and high performance of this network infrastructure are crucial for the EOSC to succeed, with high level of user satisfaction. The network requirement can be summarized as the:

- Connectivity requirement between the academic data centers, between the academic data centers and EOSC users, between academic data centers and commercial cloud providers depends on:
 - the access capacity deployed to connect the sites, and the network paths of the data transfer between the EOSC sites, and
 - advanced connectivity services usage.
- VPN usage can improve data exchange performance (see HEP and HPC community), and the security of data exchange.
- Network reliability requirement:
 - A reliable and resilient network underpinning these services is an absolute requirement.
 - Network service monitoring.
 - Network must be able to provide a monitoring solution in order to be able to identify if the problem is due to the network and where.

These requirements do not change from the first expression of requirements. One lesson learnt from the L3VPN deployment is that the site teams need to be trained about VPN local connection configuration and, even if the connection does not need to work for long, these teams have to dedicate enough resource in order to establish the VPN connection at site level.

Another important aspect highlighted was that even if there was no technical problem and the network service worked correctly, there was often no progress, and no new sites were connected to the VPN. This is mainly due to EOSCpilot project resourcing, with no staff allocation on sites and staff trying to contribute in their own free time.

Code flows between infrastructures

The interoperability of codes is an important question for a global cloud in Europe. The work done in the Pico2 project was to evaluate different ways to move code between different types of architectures and infrastructures and then to ensure portability of codes between infrastructures.

Different tools were evaluated, from packaging systems to containerized solutions. Different types of codes were tested in order to cover a wide range of uses. The main requirement is the availability of these systems on the various infrastructures in particular on HPC Tier 1 centers.

A global and homogeneous approach is needed on this topic. The approach chosen was to work with a simple software (disseq) using standard dependencies (Cmake, MPI, HDF5). Some work remains to be done for more complicated dependencies.

Containerised approach

The container approach benefits from both knowledge and experience of application containers at CCIN2P3 and the fact that the selected business case software, called Disseq¹², is a single monolithic program. This approach validated, within the PICO2 framework, that the container technology ensures code interoperability.

The Disseq code was processed in a Continuous Integration (CI) pipeline, run on the CCIN2P3 Gitlab platform. This pipeline was used to automatically produce two runnable Disseq containers, with the two most popular container technologies in this context: Singularity, from the HPC world, and Docker.

Tests were performed to ensure idempotency: both container technologies will generate containers that produce the exact same results as a traditional Disseq execution would, on the various sets of sample data that were provided.

Since containers abstract most of the technical aspects of the underlying infrastructure, application containers are probably one of the most efficient solution to ensure that the application can be executed on a large heterogeneous set of infrastructures (Computing grids, clouds, HPC platforms, etc.) such as provided by the EOSC.

Packaging approach

Packaging approach is a very important alternative to container especially on HPC infrastructures where the search for performance requires proximity to hardware. There exist many packaging systems more or less adapted to scientific computing.

We tested a few of them: nix, guix, spack and conda.

For the codes used in this benchmark, the creation of the packages was relatively simple based on standard scientific computing tools.

The main differences between these systems were that some of them can be installed in user space (spack, conda). It can be interesting for infrastructure where no packaging systems are available

Guix proposes compatible containers for DockerGuix and Nix are well suited for reproducibility.

2.1.2. WLCG/AARCv2/EOSCpilot AAI pilot for distributed authorization and authentication

X.509 certificates and VOMS have proved to be a secure and reliable solution for authentication and authorization on the Grid, but also showed usability issues and required the development of ad-hoc services and libraries to support VO-based authorization schemes in Grid middleware and experiment computing frameworks.

The need to move beyond X.509 certificates is recognised as an important objective in the HEP R&D roadmap for software and computing. This will avoid the usability issues of the current AAI and embrace recent advances in web technologies widely adopted in industry, and also enable the secure composition of computing and storage resources provisioned across heterogeneous providers in order to meet the computing needs of HL-LHC.

A flexible and usable AAI based on modern web technologies is a key enabler of such secure composition and has been a major topic of research of the recently concluded INDIGO-DataCloud project¹³.

The current Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG) AAI, is composed of the following main building blocks:

¹² Frigerio, J.-M., Rimet, F., Bouchez, A., Chancerel, E., Chaumeil, P., Salin, F., Théron, Kahlert, M. & Franc, A. (2016), "diagno-syst: a tool for accurate inventories in metabarcoding". [arXiv:1611.09410](https://arxiv.org/abs/1611.09410) [q-bio.QM]

¹³ <http://www.indigo-datacloud.eu/>

- **the trust fabric**: provided by IGTF¹⁴, tells services which are the certificate authorities (CAs) that can be trusted;
- **X.509 certificates**: issued by trusted CAs to users and services for mutual authentication purposes;
- **Proxy certificates**¹⁵: a mechanism used to implement single sign-on and delegation starting from X.509 certificates;
- **VOMS attribute certificates**¹⁶: X.509 attribute certificates embedded in proxy certificates and used to augment identity information with VO-issued authorization attributes that drive the authorization at services.

The main requirements that a novel AAI for WLCG would need to satisfy were identified:

- **Support a VO-centric authorization model**: as of today, computing and storage resources are shared in the context of a VO. Access to resources is granted, with varying levels of authorization, only to those who can prove membership in the VO by presenting an authorization token issued by a trusted central VO service;
- **Flexible authentication**: the AAI should support many authentication mechanisms, from identity federations (e.g., eduGAIN¹⁷) and social logins to X.509 certificates. Different authentication mechanisms would be mapped to different level-of-assurance profiles, so that authorization policies can be applied accordingly at services;
- **Authentication and authorization orthogonality**: authorization is decoupled from authentication mechanisms by introducing an intermediate credential, the authorization token, which provides all the information needed to grant access to shared resources;
- **Account linking and identity harmonization**: users should have the ability to link their multiple identities (e.g., their institutional login, social-media accounts, ssh keys, etc.) to their VO account;
- **Support for delegation and long-running jobs**: the AAI should support constrained delegation, where a user can delegate part of her rights to an agent or a service that acts on the user's behalf. The service must be able to further delegate a subset of these rights to other services down the line, with the explicit or implicit approval of the user;
- **Provisioning APIs**: the AAI must provide the ability to provision, manage and deprovision identity and authorization information to relying services, to enable, for instance, local or service-specific account management;
- **Integration and token translation**: the AAI must support integration with legacy or external services that cannot be modified to natively support tokens through controlled token translation.

For the WLCG AuthZ WorkingGroup¹⁸, the EOSCpilot project together with AARC supported an integrated solution, based on the INDIGO-DataCloud Identity and Access Management¹⁹ service that demonstrates how a next generation, token-based VO-aware AAI can be built in support of HEP computing use cases, while maintaining compatibility with the existing, VOMS-based AAI used by the Grid. The INDIGO IAM solution proposes the same model that was successful for VOMS. We envision a central, VO-scoped Identity and Access Management (IAM) service that deals with user authentication supporting various mechanisms and that exposes information about user's identity and authorization attributes to services in two ways:

¹⁴ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/X.509>

¹⁵ V. Welch, F. Siebenlist, I. T. Foster, J. Bresnahan, K. Czajkowski, J. Gawor, C. Kesselman, S. Meder, L. Pearlman, S. Tuecke, Security for grid services, (2003). [arXiv:cs/0306129 \[cs.CR\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/cs/0306129)

¹⁶ V. Ciaschini, V. Venturi, A. Ceccanti, The Virtual Organisation Membership Service, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1875371>

¹⁷ <https://edugain.org>

¹⁸ <https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/viewauth/LCG/WLCGAuthorizationWG>

¹⁹ <https://www.indigo-datacloud.eu/identity-and-access-management>

- via JSON Web Tokens (JWTs)²⁰ and standard OAuth²¹ and OpenID Connect²² protocol flows;
- via VOMS X.509 Attribute Certificates (ACs), as is the case for the current WLCG AAI.

IAM provides a registration service that implements a moderated enrollment flow similar to the one used in production by WLCG, with support for periodic Acceptable Usage Policy (AUP) enforcement. It supports account linking, allowing a user to link multiple identities to his VO account. Identities are then mapped to different, configurable level-of-assurance labels, which are exposed to relying services via standard OpenID Connect claims.

The IAM management dashboard, provides an intuitive tool for common administrative tasks, such as group membership and OAuth/OpenID Connect client management.

In order to fully address WLCG use cases and enable a seamless transition from an X.509- based AAI to a token-based one, IAM already implements:

- **VOMS provisioning:** a VOMS endpoint encodes user attributes as a standard VOMS attribute certificate (AC)²³;
- **CERN SSO integration:** this improves the user experience in enrollment and AUP signature management flows;
- **CERN HR database integration:** in order to support LHC VOs identity vetting process, the CERN HR database code currently used in VOMS Admin²⁴ has been extracted and refactored as a REST API. This REST API is used by a synchronization microservice to keep the VO membership information in IAM consistent with the data coming from the CERN HR database.

Token-based authentication and authorization have recently gained much attention in scientific computing:

- The EOSC-hub²⁵ project is promoting harmonization across the main European identity solutions (EGI CheckIn, B2Access, INDIGO IAM, EduTEAMS) also covering token- based authentication and authorization;
- AARC²⁶ and FIM4R²⁷ are working on recommendations and policy frameworks to support the adoption of federated identity management (FIM) by research communities;
- The OpenID Research and Education Working Group²⁸ is developing a set of profiles to ease the adoption of OpenID Connect in the Research and Education sector;
- Finally, the WLCG authorization working group is bringing together all WLCG AAI stakeholders to collect requirements and provide recommendations towards a token-based AAI.

Moving beyond X.509 certificates is recognized as a key challenge for HEP computing to improve usability, simplify the middleware stack and enable interoperability with heterogeneous computing and storage resource providers.

The INDIGO IAM solution is a token-based AAI that relies on standard authentication and authorization technologies widely adopted in industry, such as OAuth and OpenID Connect. It is the identity and authorization hub at the core of this future AAI; yet, it provides support also for existing VOMS-aware

²⁰ <https://tools.ietf.org/rfc/rfc7519.txt>

²¹ <https://tools.ietf.org/rfc/rfc6749.txt>

²² <https://openid.net/connect/>

²³ <https://www.ogf.org/documents/GFD.182.pdf>

²⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1875616>

²⁵ <https://www.eosc-hub.eu>

²⁶ <https://aarc-project.eu>

²⁷ <https://fim4r.org>

²⁸ <https://openid.net/wg/rande/>

services, thus enabling a smooth transition path. It has already been successfully integrated with existing Grid services (e.g., dCache²⁹, StoRM³⁰, FTS³¹) and other off-the-shelf components (e.g., OpenStack, Kubernetes).

Further, EOSCpilot, working with the PROMINENCE Science Demonstrator (see Section 3.2.1.) and the UK's IRIS consortium of physics and astronomy projects³², have compared using IAM and Keycloak³³ to access OpenStack resources; they each allow a user to log in with their credentials and pass group information for authorization in projects. IAM can register services only with OpenID Connect whereas Keycloak can register services with OpenID Connect or SAML. Therefore, any services that support these protocols should be compatible without any modification.

For user credentials, IAM supports linking a Google account, SAML accounts, and X.509 certificates. Keycloak supports linking accounts with SAML or any OpenID Connect identity providers. EduGAIN is a SAML based IdP, so either product would be compatible. There is also work being done to make OpenID Connect suitable for federations such as EduGAIN. GEANT is looking to create a potential OpenID Connect profile for EduGAIN, provided there is participation from communities. Additionally, Keycloak can federate external user databases, so existing LDAP or Kerberos users need not register again.

Neither solution provides functionality for users to discover or apply for roles within their dashboards, the functionality can be created externally via an API (for IAM at least). It makes sense for this to be part of a service catalogue, for users; role assignment is available in the Keycloak dashboard for administrators.

SSH logins can be achieved by prompting the user with a URL to authenticate at, doing some backend checks, and then giving the successful user a one-time password with which to log in to the session.

Given this functionality, IAM2 or Keycloak fit into the best practice blueprint outlined by AARC and should be able to support the needs of diverse communities of users doing work distributed across multiple services, sites, and countries as part of a wider AAI service

There is a new major version of IAM currently being developed, with an estimated release of mid to late 2019; it will be based on Keycloak, so it is expected that it will have much, if not all of the functionality discussed here.

Figure 2 presents the summary of the results of the Interoperability Quick Assessment Questionnaire for the INDIGO IAM solution.

²⁹ <https://dcache.org>

³⁰ <https://italiangrid.github.io/storm>

³¹ <https://fts.web.cern.ch>

³² <https://www.iris.ac.uk/>

³³ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

Figure 2: INDIGO IAM Potential Interoperability Score

2.1.3. Grid-Cloud interoperability demonstrator for HEP community

Dynamic On Demand Analysis Service (DODAS) is a Platform as a Service tool built combining several solutions and products developed by the INDIGO-DataCloud H2020 project. The testing activity carried on during the first year of the EOScpilot project progressed and increased toward the final part of project.

Tests have been performed mainly with two use cases from two distinct High Energy Physics communities: The Compact Muon Solenoid (CMS) Experiment at LHC and the Alpha Magnetic Spectrometer (AMS2) astro-particle physics experiment mounted on the ISS. In the first case, the objective was to seamlessly integrate the existing and well-established WLCG based computing model in order to bring opportunistic computing to the experiment collaboration. In the second case, the objective was to create batch system on demand. All this has been carried on in conjunction with EOSC-hub as DODAS is one of the Thematic Services providing multi-disciplinary solutions.

During the second part of the project, several services have been further integrated, in order to evaluate performance and possible weaknesses. In particular, services for transparent data access and software distribution such as Onedata and CVMFS respectively have been taken into account. Transparent data access was one of the weakness highlighted in the first year of testing mostly because no real option was offered other than XrootD that was not considered so generic. With the early evaluation of Onedata, the situation has improved both in term of scalability and performance in terms of CPU efficiency. This leaves the hope that a more mature and general-purpose software for data sharing will be available. Regarding software sharing and distribution, CVMFS confirms to be a service perfectly suitable for the integration of Grid and Clouds computing resources. Also, it is a key to deal with dynamic resource extension and thus it is a key to the elasticity.

Additional remarks and recommendations based on the DODAS experiences are listed below:

- Federation:** Federated access to underlying IaaS as already highlighted after the first year of integration and remain a key strength. In particular, the success of abstractions layers (such as PaaS Orchestrator and Infrastructure Manager) was proved in several different tests. However, a real federation requires a consolidated Authentication and Authorization mechanism, and here additional effort is still needed. DODAS integrated and successfully adopted the INDIGO IAM OpenID Connect Authorization Server, including its ecosystem such as ESACO and Token Translation Service. INDIGO IAM has been used to federate most of the authentication systems ranging from EduGAIN to egiCheckin, including several social media systems. This is a concrete starting point and should be further consolidated among scientific communities also integrating with legacy solution so that a harmonized layer can be created.
- PaaS Orchestration:** As anticipated the INDIGO PaaS Orchestrator has been fully integrated and used with great success, and we confirm that there are improvements both in the interface and in the management of IaaS ranking.
- Resource monitoring:** We confirm that we don't know about a common strategy while this is something which is strongly needed.
- Resource Accounting:** There are difficulties establishing a common vision for resource accounting. We have now started to define a strategy to extend the APEL system as an Accounting system for dynamic resources, and most importantly to accommodate accounting on opportunistic resources that are not necessarily 'on premises'.

Figure 3 presents the summary of the results of the Interoperability Quick Assessment Questionnaire for the DODAS solution.

Figure 3: DODAS Potential Interoperability Score

2.2. Data Level interoperability

The EOSCpilot Data interoperability task (T6.2) had as its objective to demonstrate how to ensure the availability of scientific data to services and users through an open cloud infrastructure. To do so, this task has produced a set of recommendations, as well as a set of technical solutions - the Data Demonstrators. These help users and programmatic services to find and access datasets across several scientific disciplines, thus enabling EOSC to be built around a more coordinated and aligned data ecosystem. For completeness, we present the following recommendations. A detailed description is available in the deliverable D6.9³⁴, “Final report on Data Interoperability”.

The six recommendations driving the data interoperability proposed strategy are:

- The data guidelines and technical solutions proposed by EOSC should be specific, common, simple, lightweight and collaborative.
- All the data resources contributing to EOSC should expose structured metadata.
- EOSC should reuse or build upon existing standards and formats and promote the use of common best practices across scientific domains.
- EOSC should propose minimum information guidelines across scientific domains, especially targeting key operational metadata which is important for services consuming data.
- EOSC should support an interconnected ecosystem of metadata catalogues as a fundamental service component to facilitate data discovery.
- EOSC should implement a monitoring service to validate standards and recommendations proposed by EOSC.

The four technical solutions that comprise the data strategy are:

- A common minimum information metadata guideline for datasets in the EOSC.
- Recommendations to establish a coordinated and interconnected ecosystem of dataset metadata catalogues.
- Adoption of Research-Schemas as a means to drive research data discoverability and accessibility.
- A set of recommendations for common properties across multiple data types.

These solutions were proposed, tested and shaped during the EOSCpilot. However, they need further development and support to be implemented and adopted.

³⁴ See: <https://www.eoscipilot.eu/content/d69-final-report-data-interoperability>.

3. SCIENCE DEMONSTRATORS AND INTEROPERABILITY ASPECTS

The EOSCpilot project followed an evidence-based approach, using a number of Science Demonstrators to show the relevance and usefulness of EOSC services and how they enable data reuse, and to drive EOSC development.

This section presents their main achievements and recommendations, with a particular focus on interoperability aspects. We also provide the interoperability evaluation results of the solutions used or developed during the lifetime of the project, based on the outcomes of the ISA³⁵ programme, Action 2016.33[1], “Assessment of trans-European systems supporting EU policies of the Interoperability solutions and common frameworks” – the *Interoperability Quick Assessment Toolkit (IQAT@)*³⁶.

3.1. First set of Science Demonstrators

EOSCpilot started with five Science Demonstrators pre-selected from a call in 2016, with project execution from January to December 2017:

- [Environmental & Earth Sciences](#) - ENVRI Radiative Forcing Integration to enable comparable data access across multiple research communities by working on data integration and harmonised access.
- [High Energy Physics](#) - WLCG: large-scale, long-term data preservation and re-use of physics data through the deployment of HEP data in the EOSC open to other research communities.
- [Social Sciences](#) – TEXTCROWD: Collaborative semantic enrichment of text-based datasets by developing new software to enable a semantic enrichment of text sources and make it available on the EOSC.
- [Life Sciences](#) - Pan-Cancer Analyses & Cloud Computing within the EOSC to accelerate genomic analysis on the EOSC and reuse solutions in other areas (e.g. for cardiovascular & neuro-degenerative diseases).
- [Physics](#) - The photon-neutron community to improve the community’s computing facilities by creating a virtual platform for all users (e.g. for users with no storage facilities at their home institutes).

3.1.1. ENVRI Radiative Forcing Integration

The refined ERFI scientific use-case addressed the forcing of land surface/ecosystem models (instead of the originally planned investigation of radiative forcing).

This pilot tested **interoperability between institution hosting data (IS-ENES) and institutions responsible for simulations (ICOS, in this case University of Helsinki)** and operate in a virtual platform provided by EGI. The EGI Open Data Platform allows integration of various data repositories in a distributed infrastructure providing a technical solution where the user can access data in repository and directly create a subset of it in the cloud without a need to download source files locally.

This science demonstrator forms a cooperation between environmental infrastructures for research of the dynamics of greenhouse gases, aerosols and clouds, and their role in radiative forcing. Targeting interoperability demands between observations and climate modeling, in an initial transfer 1.1TB of IS-ENES climate model data hosted on the DKRZ node of the Earth system Grid Federation (ESGF) was uploaded in the CYFRONET data infrastructure for model-data integration in HPC processing. CYFRONET configured **Onedata**³⁷ disk space in the EGI DataHub service to allocate 2TB in the Ceph installation. During the project, initial issues with the Oneprovider were solved by developers of Onedata and released in version “RC8”. A

³⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/actions/evaluating-and-rationalising-ict-public-administrations_en

³⁶ <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/solution/interoperability-quick-assessment-toolkit/about>

³⁷ <http://onedata.org/>

VM provided on EGI FedCloud was configured to fetch data-sets from the original data repository into the Onedata volume. Compiling and comparing model output from different sources was performed with Synda, a command line tool to search and download files from the ESGF archive. **Interoperability** is assured by exploiting Synda over the standard protocols http or gridftp.

There were a number of technical issues encountered, most of them solved or mitigations applied, and recommendations were provided, coming from the experience gained:

- Technical issues:
 - Issues with CSC-grid and personal certificates generated using DigiCert SSO service.
 - Initial Onedata problems that were solved during the project.
- Cultural Challenges:
 - **Moving and adapting services** from custom or property platforms to other infrastructure always **requires additional effort** from both sides, users and system admins.
 - Members involved in this Science Demonstrator have **different backgrounds**, and not all of them have the necessary skills to manage the interaction with the services provided by EOSC to facilitate the implementation of the pilot.
 - Mitigations and recommendations:
 - users have been **invited to access the EGI FedCloud infrastructure using the EGI VMOps dashboard**. The dashboard allows deploying VM topologies with a user-friendly interface. With the wizard, with a few clicks the user can define the technical details of the VM to be deployed in one of the cloud providers of the federation.
 - Moreover, to **facilitate the knowledge transfer**, in one of the WP5.4/WP6.3 monthly meetings, CYFRONET was invited to **report about how the Onedata software stack can be used by research communities** to implement a transparent access to datasets across different data providers.
- Interoperability issues:
 - The Onedata solution does not support any metadata transfer besides the names of the files. Therefore, interoperability depends completely on the user and there is no built-in support for automated workflows. Technical problems prevented obtaining actual results and testing of interoperability issues.

Figure 4 presents the summary of the results of the Interoperability Quick Assessment Questionnaire for the Onedata solution.

3.1.2. Pan-Cancer Analysis & Cloud Computing within the EOSC

The objective of the PCAWG (Pan-Cancer Analysis of Whole Genomes) science demonstrator was to establish a portable cloud-based federated solution for collaborative cancer genomics of more than 2800 genomes and associated health data management. The compute and data environments, accessible to European scientists for analysis, comprised 700vCPU cores, 2.6TB RAM in the EMBL-EBI Embassy Cloud in the UK, and 1000 vCPU cores, 4TB of RAM provided by Cyfronet, as well as 1000 vCPU cores, 3.9TB of RAM by ComputeCanada.

Data from the ICGC pediatric brain cancer cohort were downloaded to the ComputeCanada cloud (400 data sets, 60TB) and public data from the 1000 Genomes project (50TB) was uploaded onto the CYFRONET environment from the EMBL/EBI data servers utilizing CYFRONET's Oneprovider software. Significant storage space was provided by EMBL (4.9 TB volume storage), CYFRONET (1 PB NFS storage) and ComputeCanada (62 TB volume and 200 TB NFS storage). A total amount of approx. 400 samples (100 TB) was processed with the Butler scientific framework, which has been set up and tested at the three globally distributed cloud computing environments, all based on the OpenStack platform. The services included monitoring solution and self-healing modules by Butler.

Figure 4: Onedata Potential Interoperability Score

The science demonstrator has described the demand for a **uniform identity and access management** across environments.

CYFRONET addressed scalability issues encountered using the recommended service, Onedata/Oneprovider, in the context of the HNSciCloud project and stability issues encountered at the CYFRONET environment with the allocated storage and data staging mechanism (Oneprovider). Storage throughput issues faced at the ComputeCanada environment were solved during the project.

3.1.3. Research with Photons & Neutrons

Reproducible scientific analysis requires accessible software environments, workflows and data. Scientific workflows at Photon and Neutron facilities access data, which in general are too large to take home, thus this SD aimed to avoid the need to transfer data sets to user systems, while offering cloud-based workflows on shared, distributed systems instead. Solutions are applicable for data embargo periods as well as for open data, thus addressing secure access strategies.

Probing auto-scaling deployments of experiment services and user defined software stacks in cloud-based container orchestration clusters, identified the gaps and proposed concepts for the federation of on-premise clouds with EOSC, leveraging federated AAI solutions, offering a service oriented collaborative platform.

Starting with the well-established **dCache**³⁸ storage system, the **testbed assessed the interoperability between different storage systems**, leveraging a broad spectrum of standard protocols for data access. Avoiding the need to mount filesystem in containers, therefore mitigating scenarios where container users escalate to root privileges on shared file systems, the WebDav protocol over https surfaced as the choice for data access in this SD. In addition, AFS, CVMFS, conventional (NetApp) SMB/NFS-shares, and the local /

³⁸ <http://dcache.org/>

federated Nextcloud instance (also backed by dCache) provided data exchange between VMs and external resources.

The underlying VM clusters and Container Orchestration Engines on the OpenStack cloud at DESY used 512 physical CPUs (924 logical) and 7.3 TB RAM. The OpenStack module Magnum was tested for the provisioning of Kubernetes Clusters and Docker Swarm, but it was decided to provision clusters based on HEAT templates and cloud-init scripts due to greater flexibility and lower complexity.

During the project phase DESY opened access to their cloud resources from outside of the internal network. Regarding future access to real time data from various experiments like the European XFEL, the integration of the local InfiniBand fabrics and HPC file systems was discussed and gaps were identified.

The SD deployed parts of the CrystFEL framework as microservices and examined proof of concept analysis with roughly 1 TB data from serial femto-second x-ray crystallography. This is a complex, non-redistributable software stack, which is free to use by academia and non-profit organizations. The most important platforms operated were OpenStack, OpenWhisk, Kubernetes, GitLab, Kafka, Docker and dCache. As graphical frontend for scientific workflows served an auto-scaling cloud deployment of Jupyter Notebooks.

Avoiding depending only on the local LDAP and Kerberos accounts, federated AAI based on the integration of the DESY Identity provider (IdP) with EGI Check-In was achieved and will persist on involved cloud systems operated by DESY.

Figure 5 presents the summary of the results of the Interoperability Quick Assessment Questionnaire for the dCache solution.

Figure 5: dCache Potential Interoperability Score

Figure 6 presents the summary of the results of the Interoperability Quick Assessment Questionnaire for the Photon & Neutron scientific workflows solution.

Figure 6: Photon & Neutron scientific workflows solution Potential Interoperability Score

3.1.4. Collaborative semantic enrichment of text - based datasets (TEXTCROWD)

TEXTCROWD is a cloud-based NLP tool, developed as one of the Scientific Demonstrators of the EOSCpilot project for working on the collaborative semantic enrichment of text sources, and to make it available on the EOSC. The tool is intended for processing textual reports and can be especially useful in disciplines such as archaeology, where the main information is contained in free text documents rather than in relational databases or other structured datasets. TEXTCROWD can be also used to establish an advanced machine-learning scenario for producing semantic metadata ready to be integrated with information coming from different domains.

TEXTCROWD could also enable researchers to generate and revise the enrichment of collections of texts using the automatic NLP tools provided. Additional important features concern the produced output. TEXTCROWD is able to generate metadata out of the knowledge extracted from the documents into a semantic format, such as RDF, and to produce actual “translations” from natural to machine understandable languages. In its final release, TEXTCROWD is implementing an NLP cloud service capable of processing Italian archaeological excavation reports by recognizing relevant archaeological entities and linking them to each other on linguistic bases.

From a technical point of view, the TEXTCROWD testbed is composed of a modular system operating on the cloud by means of specific interfaces. The low-level processing algorithms for the initial pilot employed the Stanford GATE framework³⁹ and a set of OpenNLP⁴⁰ components for the Italian language. Following the initial evaluation, it was decided to adopt some of the low-level Italian language processing resources produced for

³⁹ <https://gate.ac.uk>

⁴⁰ <https://opennlp.apache.org>

the (EU funded) OpeNER⁴¹ project, such as language identification, tokenization and part of speech tagging. Both sets of third-party NLP resources were combined in the final NER system for Named Entities Recognition and Resolution. The original NER pipeline was able to directly annotate “Place” and “Person” entities using the OpeNER project’s webservices. The TEXTCROWD NER system for Italian language archaeological text is also able to annotate “Artefacts”, “Colors”, “Materials”, “Periods”, “Places”, “Sites”, “Techniques” and “Timespans” entities.

TEXTCROWD was initially trained on a set of vocabularies and terminological tools, and with a corpus of about 100 Italian archaeological excavation reports. After executing on Italian archaeological text, the algorithm is able to produce information encoded in CIDOC CRM RDF format⁴², GATE XML, Inline HTML and list of annotations in standard forms.

In its final release, TEXTCROWD was deployed within D4Science⁴³, a cloud infrastructure offering advanced features including:

- Authentication and authorization facilities for federated identity management.
- Deployment, configuration and benchmarking interfaces.
- Controlled code execution and debugging features.
- Cloud folders for shared and personal storage.
- APIs exposure and querying for external interaction.

D4Science also offers the possibility to set up Virtual Research Environments (VREs), kinds of virtual labs where scholars could work together in collaborative scenarios to address specific research questions.

D4Science was able to supply an ideal hosting environment for TEXTCROWD, which did not present particular performance issues within the D4Science environment. This is because the NLP process is not particularly demanding in terms of computing resources required to be deployed at runtime, and textual documents tend to be small in size. Possibly storage and processing issues may arise if there are a higher number of small files to be processed - we envisage millions of potential reports needing NLP analysis. However, since textual datasets do not need to be processed altogether and, once processed, they become almost completely static, this is not regarded as a real issue in terms of scalability.

From a user perspective, the TEXTCROWD-D4Science cloud service allows users to upload and store textual documents in personal cloud folders, perform NLP and NER operations, trigger the semantic enrichment process and obtain the output CIDOC CRM information in RDF. The web-service basis of the D4Science platform allows the NLP application to augment the NLP pipeline with specific resources by means of external web service that can be invoked from within D4Science itself. Results can be stored in the cloud, uploaded in a triple store or in another semantic enabled system, and reused within the same context or in another VRE on the same infrastructure.

The use of standard technologies and a modular architecture, easily deployable in different cloud contexts, make TEXTCROWD a flexible tool suitable to be extended and readapted for the use in different scenarios. Integration with other Science Demonstrators has been evaluated within EOSCpilot. In particular, **interoperability has been established with the VisualMedia pilot**, developed by ISTI-CNR for automatic metadata extraction from controlled lists or textual documents for 2D and 3D models; and also **with the Frictionless Data Exchange pilot**, intended for synchronization of annotated documents repositories across the Web. A possible **interoperability with external services**, like B2DROP, B2SHARE and OAI-PMH compatible repositories, has also been envisaged.

⁴¹ <http://www.opener-project.eu>

⁴² <http://cidoc-crm.org>

⁴³ <https://www.d4science.org>

Tests for its applicability outside the EOSC framework have also been carried out. The tool was deployed as part of the NLPhub framework, a Virtual Research Environment developed under the PARTHENOS initiative⁴⁴ intended to combine the potential and the specific features of different NLP tools in order to create advanced software pipelines for processing streams of documents of various language, topic and provenance, in a recursive way.

At the end of its development cycle, TEXTCROWD has reached an excellent level of development. It has attracted interest and shown potential for applicability in different ways and fields, encouraging further improvements, and being selected as one of the **potential candidates to become a service for the EOSC Marketplace and the EOSC Portal**.

The developments of TEXTCROWD also continues beyond the specific scope of the EOSCpilot initiative. Within the ARIADNEplus framework⁴⁵, for instance, it will play a fundamental role for indexing excavation reports and enriching the ARIADNEplus Catalogue. To empower the tool and adapt it to other domains and extend its capabilities to other languages, its new release is equipped with innovative Supervised Machine Learning algorithms (Conditional Random Fields and Neural Networks) to learn an entity recognition model from examples of documents annotated by experts. The entity recognition model can efficiently process streams with large amounts of documents, populating a structured knowledge base. The learned entity recognition model can also be used to drive the selection of the documents to be annotated by experts, so as to better exploit the human annotation effort (Active Learning).

Figure 7 presents the summary of the results of the Interoperability Quick Assessment Questionnaire for the TEXTCROWD solution.

Figure 7: TEXTCROWD Potential Interoperability Score

⁴⁴ <http://www.parthenos-project.eu>

⁴⁵ <https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

3.1.5. WLCG Open Science Demonstrator - Data Preservation and Re-Use through Open Data Portal (DPHEP)

The WLCG (Worldwide LHC Computing Grid) concentrated on long-term preservation and re-use of HEP data, documentation and associated software. Interoperability was targeted by the use of PIDs (persistent identifiers) in a non-community specific manner that resolve to a virtualized environment that runs in Cloud, Grid and many other environments. Primary storage platforms used were B2SHARE⁴⁶ and Zenodo⁴⁷, hosting more than 100 TB of open data.

With the objective to provide scalable “digital library” services where documentation is referenced by a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), the project used services provided by OpenAIRE (Zenodo), EGI Engage (CVMFS – already offered by EGI InSPIRE SA3, led by CERN) and a Trustworthy Digital Repository (TDR).

The beginning of the project encountered delays in finding a host for the Trustworthy Digital Repository (TDR) and the final report states: “*The objective and the simple goal outlined above was not achieved*”; the services envisaged were not interoperable at the moment of the testing by the Science Demonstrator.

3.2. Second Set of Science Demonstrators

The first EOSCpilot Open Call for Science Demonstrators in April 2017 resulted in five new Science Demonstrators with execution from July 2017 to June 2018:

- [Energy Research – PROMINENCE](#): HPCaaS for Fusion - Access to HPC class nodes for the Fusion Research community through a cloud interface.
- [Earth Sciences – EPOS/VERCE](#): Virtual Earthquake and Computational Earth Science e-science environment in Europe.
- [Life Sciences / Genome Research](#): Life Sciences Datasets: Leveraging EOSC to offload updating and standardizing life sciences datasets and to improve studies reproducibility, reusability and interoperability.
- [Life Sciences / Structural Biology](#): CryoEM Workflows: Linking distributed data and data analysis resources as workflows in Structural Biology with cryo Electron Microscopy: Interoperability and reuse.
- [Physical Sciences / Astronomy](#): LOFAR Data: Easy access to LOFAR data and knowledge extraction through Open Science Cloud.

3.2.1. HPCaaS for Fusion (PROMINENCE)

Improvements in sensor technology, the demands for higher fidelity modelling with in-built uncertainty quantification and more widely used software packages for modelling and analysis are driving a demand for computational resources that often outstrip the locally available capacity. While classical batch systems are at least part of the solution, many modelling and analysis codes require significant execution time (between days and months), increasing the ‘time to science’ for users waiting in a queue. In many cases, this has resulted in a classical ‘hybrid’ cloud solution which allows users at a site to make use of resources in a public cloud for a fee. However, the disadvantage of this solution is that often the workflows are built around a proprietary API which leads to vendor lock-in, with significant effort required to migrate from one cloud provider to another. With the potential of long wait times, even HPC class jobs requiring MPI may be better run on non-optimized resources than wait in a queue for more appropriate resources.

The PROMINENCE service aims to address this by **providing users with a batch system type interface** using REST APIs to allow submission of a job which can be run on any cloud compatible site, whether that is local, national, European, global, academic or commercial, based on a specific configurable allowed list. The main

⁴⁶ <https://b2share.eudat.eu/>

⁴⁷ <https://zenodo.org/>

requirements from the user perspective is that jobs must **make use of containerisation technologies**. This also imposes some limitations on the type of jobs being executed; any code under ‘export control’ should be verified that it can be run off site, and the list of possible cloud providers may need to be restricted based on this, and applications making use of licensed commercial software requiring access to a licence server (such as the NAG library, MATLAB or IDL).

By design, PROMINENCE, while it can be used as an interface to a single cloud provider, is really designed for opportunistic use of resources. Once a user submits a ‘job spec’ to the service (giving information such as the number of cores, the total memory requirement, the container image location and information on how to access any input data), the service itself will try and instantiate an appropriately sized cluster on each of the cloud providers allowed in turn. In the case of failure, any VMs created are destroyed and the next cloud in the list is tried. Once a suitable cluster meeting the user requirements has been created the container image is then downloaded and executed. The results are moved to a defined storage location and an access URL is returned to the user. Finally, the VMs in the cluster are destroyed and can be made use of again.

In terms of underlying services, we have tested three containerization technologies: Docker, **udocker** (provided by INDIGO DataCloud) and **Singularity**. While all these have been successful, we have found that **udocker** actually provides the best generic solution and is the simplest for users to make use of. **Infrastructure Manager** (again provided by INDIGO) is used to deploy and configure infrastructure across clouds. Open Policy Agent is being used to determine which clouds meet the users’ requirements and to rank them. The underlying management of jobs is handled by HTCondor. Authentication is currently based on **INDIGO IAM**.

This service has been successfully tested on the UK IRIS e-infrastructure (in collaboration with STFC), several sites in the EGI FedCloud and on two of the major public cloud providers (Google Cloud Platform and Azure). One **limitation** to the services future usability within EOSC lies in the **current requirement to order resources on the FedCloud rather than fulfilling request on-demand**. Unless this ordering process can be made highly automated and responsive (taking less than a minute), then FedCloud may not represent the ideal solution. However, OCRE⁴⁸, with the offer of a pay-per-use model and pre-emptible VMs may offer a very good solution in the medium term.

3.2.2. EGA Life Science Datasets Leveraging EOSC - Leveraging EOSC to offload updating and standardizing life sciences datasets and to improve studies reproducibility, reusability and interoperability

The Science Demonstrator aimed to explore the feasibility of data reproducibility and data re-mastering in genomics. Both reproducibility and re-mastering require pipeline portability and the availability of metadata describing the tools and resources used within a given pipeline.

The SD developed pipelines and security mechanisms to upload (FAIRify) and process genome datasets and metadata on cloud resources and make them available for portable clients. The pipelines were deposited in Dockstore⁴⁹, an open platform for sharing containerized scientific workflows and tools. In order to facilitate their re-use, deposited pipeline containers were described through the meta-data available at Dockstore plus additional fields that were considered relevant basing on our experience.

The services are running at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC). Data sets (BAM files) are large, too large to be processed seamlessly on currently available cloud resources. In addition, auxiliary files are needed for processing the datasets. For this purpose, the project expressed interest in integrating metadata schemas with the **B2FIND Metadata Catalog**. Multiple versions of domain specific data analysis software were used, exploiting the NextFLOW⁵⁰ workflow manager and GoNL pipeline as containerized version (Singularity). Multiple versions of the analysis software posed a challenge on findability and reproducibility, the same

⁴⁸ www.ocre-project.eu

⁴⁹ <https://dockstore.org/>

⁵⁰ <https://www.nextflow.io/>

applies to auxiliary files involved. Not all modules and tools are ready to run in containers and integrate in cloud environments.

Dealing with sensitive data, the project had to address special security challenges and policies.

The work of the SD demonstrates that is technically possible to reproduce at a high degree genomics data, and that currently available tools, language and repositories are providing useful means to foster reproducibility and data refreshing in science. The resulting workflow application has been deposited in the Dockstore catalogue⁵¹.

Regarding the challenges encountered during the project and recommendations or mitigation actions for the future:

(a) For scientific workflow reproducibility, promote the adoption of best practices such as:

- describe the computational environment with a package manager such Conda/Bioconda whenever possible.
- Capture the computational environment using a container technology eg. Docker or Singularity. The container should be depositing in a community collection like BioContainers⁵².
- Use workflow systems like Nextflow to enable portable deployments across different cloud and clusters with minimal changes.
- Deposit the data analysis code into a public source code management platform.
- Disseminate the resulting application through an open catalog like Dockstore which implement FAIR principles and community best practices.

(b) To foster interoperability:

- Nextflow workflow manager was adopted to implement the SD's pipelines. Nextflow is an emerging language for genomic pipelines and it is among the ones accepted by Dockstore, a repository endorsed by GA4GH for sharing Docker-based tools. GA4GH is a global effort involving major stakeholders for the definition of standards in biology and the implementation of tools service the whole biological community.
- A FAIR representation of the objects and their relationships is required. FAIR-compliant semantic repositories address issues encountered during the project and the SD thinks that this kind of repository is missing in the EOSC ecosystem.
- The experience provided by this SD proves the need to foster the adoption of standards to describe and document genomic pipelines. Even if the field is moving toward open science policies, pipeline portability and documentation are still perceived by providers as time consuming tasks that are not fully part of their scientific obligations.
- Standards and specific metadata to describe pipelines, and long-term repositories for such artifacts, are a priority to foster reproducibility in genomics. Based on the experience gained through the project, it is suggested to implement a universal method valid across several scientific fields on which it should be possible for each step of a pipeline to declare: the used tool, its version, the input, the options and the output. Finally, the presence of links to software containers to the used tools would provide a determinant contribution to data reproducibility. These containers should be available for as long as the raw data is, in order to keep the whole experiment reproducible.
- Continuous training is required to form a new generation of scientist more engaged in adopting open science policies and behaviors.

⁵¹ <https://dockstore.org/workflows/github.com/CRG-CNAG/EOSC-Pilot>

⁵² <https://biocontainers.pro/>

3.2.3. Virtual Earthquake and Computational Earth Science e-science environment in Europe (EPOS/VERCE)

The demonstrator **democratises access to HPC simulation codes, data and workflows** for the evaluation of Earth models. It aims at enhancing the services of the VERCE portal and integrate the EGI FedCloud Infrastructure as the main data-intensive computational service provider for Misfit Analysis Workflows. These workflows use authorization delegation mechanisms to connect to remote data-stores and web services and produce provenance data. The mechanism to manage such functionalities should work seamlessly across different resources and networks.

Among the main achievements are the **extension of the Forward Modeling tool** hosted by the gateway with an additional simulation code (SPECFEM3D_GLOBE) and the upgrade of the gateway to gUSE 3.7.5. This was needed, together with several specific fixes and extensions, to support the FedCloud OCCl interface. This should have included the support of a delegation mechanism to authorise the transfer of data from the cloud to the self-managed iRODS instance. A new release of the DCI-Bridge Virtual Appliance (VA) used by the science gateway to be interoperable with the EOSC cloud infrastructure has been developed. The VA is now registered in the EGI AppDB Cloud marketplace. The lineage and provenance services and repository have been upgraded to a later version of the S-ProvFlow API and storage system. These have been deployed in its containerised version within SCAI resources.

After upgrading the whole gateway framework, the processing workflows enabling the Misfit analysis (data download, preprocessing and misfit) have been refactored to support their execution on the FedCloud, in addition to the current HPC resources. The **pilot used cloud resources provided by three providers of the EGI Federation (IN2P3-IRES, SCAI and HG-09-Okeanos-Cloud)**. However, data access delegation via Proxy did not work as expected since the X.509 certificate could not be copied and used automatically within the VMs.

Concerning **AAI**, on a development copy of the Gateway and its services, an **evaluation of authentication methods has been carried out**. The portal has been extended to allow the retrieval of Per-User Sub-Proxy certificates from the eToken proxy certificate service for Workflows, additionally to its community-specific IdP. In a second evaluation, **login via OpenID Connect** through the **EGI Check-In** service has been **successfully validated**, though in the latter case, the retrieval of the required X.509 certificate via the RCauth service could not be finished successful during the runtime of the demonstrator.

Regarding the **interoperability of the systems adopted**, it seems that the **OCCI and the support of the gUSE technical framework** from the **EOSC will not be guaranteed**. This will require additional investments and a strategy to dismiss and replace third party software that will not comply with the supported interfaces. The reproducibility and traceability problem should start to be addressed structurally (towards a FAIR e-infrastructure), scaling from ad-hoc solutions to generic services, or fostering compatibility. **Computational tools** offered by EOSC **should be already integrated** within a **framework for reproducibility**, offering possibilities of adaptation to the use-cases (granularity, privacy rules and visibility), and contextualization to the user's domain. Ultimately, multi-architecture and scale-up support offered by the EOSC computational services should offer the possibility for expert research-developers to develop serverless workflows, where available resources are allocated and scaled dynamically, removing the burden of configuring specific providers. **Such mechanisms should be provided or brokered by the EOSC**, which should also advertise to stakeholders the adoption of compliant tools.

3.2.4. CryoEM – Life Science Data Workflows

CryoEM **targets shared services**, accessible for different facilities in Europe, for image processing workflows with enhanced reproducibility, by linking to acquired data and software and fully describe image processing steps. During the project a number of achievements were reported in using the infrastructures and services made available, that helped also in improving the SD's own workflows and solutions:

- On the storage backend, the public database EMPIAR, workflow files were made available in the self-describing JSON format.
- The Scipion software framework⁵³ was exploited to manage image processing pipelines used for electron microscopy (EM).
- The image processing pipelines are normally carried out in large EM facilities and tools were developed to be able to export the workflow as well as the data in a way that the early stages can be fully automated.
- The EMDB and EMPIAR coordinator (the largest public databases for EM) were contacted so that structural biologists can submit the data as well as their workflow to these databases, and any other researcher can reuse the data and reproduce the same results as the original researcher, up to the estimation of the microscope aberrations.
 - An agreement was reached to accept the workflow descriptions sent by Scipion as well as incorporating the web viewer to allow their visualization.
- The Common Workflow Language (CWL) was assessed during the project, as a description of the processes performed
 - Although promising, at the moment no further step has been taken, since this has to be decided community wise.

Some issues were encountered for which the SD made recommendations on how to address or mitigate them in the future:

(a) Technical challenges:

- There is no large repository for acquired data, so that at acquisition time, the data cannot be transferred along with its FAIR descriptor to any repository.
Mitigation - implement a mechanism of data storage so that the metadata and workflows associated with the acquisition are deposited in some common place (currently there is no hardware for this), and eventually recovery for their submission to the final structural biology databases.

(b) Political challenges:

- EMPIAR is only accepting data associated with final results. There is no place for new acquisitions to deposit their metadata and associated workflows. Eventually, this pilot could be regularly used at facilities. A mechanism for user identification (either the facility, or the final user) should be provided if EOSC is to provide hardware for the image processing.
Mitigation - Definition of a policy for acquisition metadata and workflows, and another one for user authentication (technically this is solved) for using the EOSC machines.

(c) Cultural challenges:

- Structural biologists are not used to machines in the cloud, EGI, etc. Many of them do not know what options they have available.
Mitigation - Training and dissemination of information on the use of cloud machines.

3.2.5. Astronomy Open Science Cloud access to LOFAR data

The LOFAR Astronomy Open Science Cloud shares existing LOFAR data in accordance with FAIR principles, and enables container-based online data processing. The objective was to **build a distributed system to locate, access and extract scientific results from the LOFAR archive**, and that is able to run on a variety of platforms, such as MacBook, Linux, SURFsara resources HPC cloud and Cartesius supercomputer. During the project a number of achievements in using the infrastructures and services made available were reported, and that also helped to improve the SD's own workflows and solutions.

⁵³ <http://scipion.i2pc.es>

Some of these achievements, together with some final recommendations on how to mitigate or address them, are as follows:

- Federated authentication was integrated with B2ACCESS.
- The strong interoperability demand led to the use of the Toil workflow engine⁵⁴ and the CWL standards for portable workflows that build on existing tools like Xenon, Docker, and Virtuoso.
 - Demonstrated that the Common Workflow Language standards are sufficient to enable the portable description of radio astronomy data analysis pipeline via three real-world examples.
- For all involved software building blocks, Debian packages were built and published.
- Storage was allocated at B2SHARE and PSNC/FZJ resources and enhancements for data access and notebook-based processing were examined.
- The data was processed and viewed with domain specific tools comprising Prefactor⁵⁵ (calibration), Presto⁵⁶ (framework to search specific signals in LOFAR data) and Spiel⁵⁷ (radio telescope simulator).
- Enhancing containerization solutions, the project used Docker, Singularity and udocker. Due to security concerns using Docker, a preference was expressed for Singularity as container technology. However, GPU acceleration introduces rigid dependencies on software version relations on the host and in the containers, e.g. Cuda Drivers, NVIDIA kernel modules. This poses limitations on portability; a workaround was only described for Docker.
- Work targeting the Mesos⁵⁸ scheduler on HPC cloud could not be finished.

Technical challenges:

- The CWL + Singularity deployment on the SURFsara grid cluster was not evaluated for lack of support for CWL on that system, although this type of cluster is one of the most fitting systems for processing large LOFAR datasets.
- Retrieving data from a tape backend and large data volumes at the level of tens to hundreds of terabytes is a major challenge when the data are not local.
- Mitigations:
 - Support for CWL and, in particular container based, preferably Singularity, deployments on all EOSC clusters (including grid/HPC).
 - A wide(r) deployment of high capacity network connections between computing centers; on demand point to point.

Political challenges:

- Sustainability of services in a collaborative environment: Who takes responsibility for defining, building and supporting community-oriented services? For example, Infrastructure provider, Expertise center, Research support organization. Each needs acknowledgement and visibility.
- Mitigations:
 - Direct collaborations involving all stakeholders, transparent propagation of acknowledgements (supported e.g. by standardized policies).

Interoperability Issues:

- Addressed during the project at the level of Proof of Concept:
 - Portable and flexible pipeline/workflow definition & deployment using containers.
 - Data access and storage (FAIR data repository).
 - User Interface for definition & starting pipelines.

⁵⁴ <https://toil.readthedocs.io/>

⁵⁵ <https://github.com/lofar-astron/prefactor>

⁵⁶ <https://www.cv.nrao.edu/~sransom/presto/>

⁵⁷ <https://github.com/gijzelaerr/spiel>

⁵⁸ <https://mesos.apache.org/>

- Not covered within EOSCpilot (status 13/11/2018):
 - Make workflow useable over more systems.
 - High bandwidth connectivity.
 - Federated access.

Figure 8 presents the summary of the results of the Interoperability Quick Assessment Questionnaire for the LOFAR SD AAI integration solution.

Figure 8: LOFAR SD's AAI integration Potential Interoperability Score

3.3. Third Set of Science Demonstrators

The second EOSCpilot Open Call for Science Demonstrators in August/September 2017 resulted in five new Science Demonstrators with execution from December 1, 2017, to November 2018:

- [Generic Technologies: Frictionless](#) Data Exchange Across Research Data, Software and Scientific Paper Repositories.
- [Physical Sciences - Astro Sciences: VisIVO](#): Data Knowledge Visual Analytics Framework for Astrophysics.
- [Social Sciences and Humanities \(SSH\): VisualMedia](#): a service for sharing and visualizing visual media files on the web.
- [Life Sciences and Health Research: Bioimaging](#) - Mining a large image repository to extract new biological knowledge about human gene function.
- [Environmental & Earth Sciences - Hydrology](#): Switching on the EOSC for Reproducible Computational Hydrology by FAIRifying eWaterCycle and SWITCH-ON.

3.3.1. Frictionless Data Exchange Across Research Data, Software and Scientific Paper Repositories

The Science Demonstrator aimed at building a cross-disciplinary network of repositories to efficiently and reliably exchange scholarly communications, allowing for highly scalable exchange of data across repositories. This involves the design and implementation of a scalable client for accessing both, metadata and full texts.

The Science Demonstrator managed a number of achievements in the use of the ResourceSync protocol, and its improvement and use by other SDs, like TEXTCROWD and WLCG HEP:

- Collected baseline data for a comparison of the ResourceSync protocol with OAI-PMH.
- Evaluation of three different ResourceSync setups (standard, batch and materialized dump) across several datasets of scientific publications.
- New synchronization approach proposed to the ResourceSync community. The new approach has also been developed and tested, and the source code is released on GitHub Repository⁵⁹.
- A report has been written together with TEXTCROWD SD on how ResourceSync can improve the discoverability and interoperability of this Science Demonstrator tool.
- A report has been written together with WLCG HEP SD on how ResourceSync can help address and mitigate the Science Demonstrator challenges encountered.
- Supported ARC (OpenAIRE) in their efforts in adopting ResourceSync harvesting from our projects ResourceSync endpoint called Publisher Connector.
- Established a commercial collaboration with Naver Academic⁶⁰ who now harvest data from the CORE aggregator⁶¹ to Naver Academic in production using ResourceSync.

Interoperability aspects:

- The experience gained through running this Science demonstrator proved that ResourceSync is a valid approach on improving the interoperability at scale. Adoption from big providers is the next thing to pursue. Policy push and recommendations from across the sector would help in its wider adoption.

3.3.2. Mining a large image repository to extract new biological knowledge about human gene function

This science demonstrator performed a comprehensive machine learning analysis on large cloud-based collections of image-based, genome-scale data sets. They **demonstrated the interoperability of the infrastructure that allows users to run their own analysis via the cloud on publicly available image data sets in the TIFF format**. Data were made available in the IDR repository, data sources were mounted per NFS and the OpenLava software was used to create LSF-like environments. Workflows were analyzed and dependencies on software versions were identified. With respect to scaling the SD deployment, the provisioning of better image access through API enhancements was proposed.

Resources were organized on the EMBASSY cloud comprising ~200 low-memory CPUs at the beginning of the project and ~20 high-memory CPUs at later stages. The VMs were operated leveraging OpenStack software defined networking.

The SD encountered a number of technical problems and made some observations and recommendations for the future:

Issues:

- Setting up and configuring a tenancy in the cloud requires a level of IT expertise beyond what can be expected from most computational biologists, and is definitely beyond the reach of cell biologists who would only occasionally need to run image analysis tasks. In fact, the project wouldn't even have

⁵⁹ <https://github.com/oacore/rs-aggregator>

⁶⁰ <https://academic.naver.com/>

⁶¹ <https://core.ac.uk/>

been able to start and subsequently run without the excellent and regular support of EOSCpilot Shepherds. In particular, several stumbling blocks were identified:

- Defining the parameters of the tenancy for the project was not easy and took time. For example, how many vCPUs and how much RAM they should have are parameters that depend both on the underlying cloud technology (e.g. what hardware is available, how fast it is...), on the software used (how efficient it is both in terms of memory use and computation speed) and on the data to be processed.
- Creating a compute cluster and deploying software across all nodes are tasks that are typically done by the IT team supporting an HPC, but which in the cloud are transferred to the user. Having to write and run scripts with obscure parameters is going to be a major obstacle to adoption.
- Defining the deployment size of a data processing pipeline can be difficult because requirements are not always comparable from one data set to another. A lot of computation time has been spent on various issues including adapting and testing the code to run in the cloud environment. Although cost wasn't taken into account for this project, we surmise that this could become prohibitively expensive depending on the cost model adopted for cloud access.
- The cloud environment is not as flexible as a local HPC:
 - Meeting the requirements of the different parts of the computation requires a complete tear-down and recreation of the cluster whereas, in a local HPC, one can just specify the resource requirements for each job. The alternative is over-specification of the cloud tenancy requirements to cover all needs.
 - The cloud didn't offer a high performance shared file system which means that I/O-bound operations need to be rethought and substantially reworked compared to a local HPC with such a file system.
- Much standard image analysis software requires image data to be in files on the local file system. Most of this software would need to be rewritten to get their input directly from object storage as typically used in the cloud. The alternative is to add a preprocessing step to save object storage data to a local file, which adds overhead to all computation but could be mitigated by availability of a high-performance file system.

Mitigations:

- User-friendly and user accessible platform to set up and provision nodes in a cloud environment targeted at non-specialist users and streamlined and quick interaction with IT support staff.
- Because defining the deployment size of an established data processing pipeline can be difficult, a generous cost model that doesn't penalize testing of pipelines and overprovisioning of tenancies should be considered.
- Provisioning of high-performance shared file system for I/O bound operations.
- Standardized environment and tools for deploying software.

3.3.3. VisIVO: Data Knowledge Visual Analytics Framework for Astrophysics

The objective of the VISIVO science demonstrator focuses on publishing a data analysis and visualization environment fully integrated with a relevant set of astrophysical datasets. The Data Knowledge Visual Analytics Framework for Astrophysics is a visual analytics environment based on the Virtual Observatory standards and the ViaLactea framework.

It was implemented on local cloud resources and federated using EGI FedCloud resources. The ViaLactea Science Gateway, developed on the WS-PGRADE/gUSE portal framework, was used to exploit cloud resources and was subject to several issues and enhancements at the beginning of the project. It exposes APIs on cloud VMs, used by the Visual Analytics client to compute Spectral Energy Distributions employing theoretical models and simulations. The VMs on EGI FedCloud used public IPs and ports to connect with the DCI-Bridge, which was used by the Science Gateway to run the scientific workflows. The solution was made available

under Open Source, Apache License V2, in the EGI AppDB. Targeting reliable interoperability, it exposes two RESTful APIs: (i) the gUSE Remote API and (ii) the recently developed CAGE (Cloud for Astrophysics GatEway) APIs, both using open data formats like JSON, XML and gUSE WMS.

On EGI resources, a storage containing ~400GB astrophysics survey data as well as related metadata for queries and access the archive was organized for sustainable open access employing the ViaLactea Knowledge Base software architecture and services based on the Virtual Observatory standards.

Finally, the ViaLactea science gateway was extended to connect with EGI Check-In AAI for federated user authentication.

Figure 9 presents the summary of the results of the Interoperability Quick Assessment Questionnaire for the VisIVO solution.

Figure 9: VisIVO Potential Interoperability Score

3.3.4. Switching on the EOSC for Reproducible Computational Hydrology by FAIR-ifying eWaterCycle and SWITCH-ON

Central to the science of hydrology is the localized nature of the medium through which water flows. This fact leads to a large number of hydrological models, specifically made for a certain region (catchment). The fact that these **models are made by different individuals**, in different programming languages severely hinders their re-use and reproducibility. This in turn is leading to a “crisis of reproducibility” in Hydrology. This science demonstrator aimed to create a fully FAIR Hydrological forecasting system, combining local and global models. With this it showcases and hope to demonstrate best practices on how data as well as software can be made FAIR in Hydrology.

There was an **assessment** of the various input data sets required for the SD. Even determining the FAIRness of a dataset proved problematic, as critical information needed for this assessment such as guarantees of long-term availability of a repository is often not publicised. In the end, it was decided that creating a local copy of the required input data was the best course of action, though recognising that this cannot yet be considered FAIR.

Using a combination of the **CWL** standard for workflows, **Cylc**, and **Docker software containers**, the SD was able to create a fully reproducible (low resolution) version of the eWaterCycle forecast. Output data is stored via **Onedata**, and available for analysis in a notebook environment, as well as visualization in a web application.

The forecast is now running daily, without any manual intervention. The SD plans to deploy the system to one or more supercomputer systems and increase the resolution of the model. On this version we can do a verification of model output to assess its scientific merit. In addition there is a plan to integrate the work done in this demonstrator into the larger eWaterCycle⁶² II project, with a focus on FAIR Hydrological modelling.

With the objective of opening access to software for large scale simulation-based science and to deploy it in Common Workflow language (CWL) workflows, this project also set up archives for input and output data on Onedata Storage elements. In containerized deployments, they provided access to domain specific tools like SWITCH-On and eWaterCycle, supporting CWL, BMI and OpenDA. Data is organized in the NetCDF format.

Technical challenges & recommendations:

- This demonstrator makes use of the Onedata system. Specifically, a storage node at CNAF. There were some stability issues with this experimental node.
- The reason we used Onedata was to have easy access to our data from all our environments. For some, installing software and creating mounts is problematic, so for those we would like to have a client application rather than installing Onedata into the system.
- The Onedata solution solely relies on FUSE mounts and that caused some issues getting going on the infrastructure used. The mitigation was to install Onedata as a system service on the cloud infrastructure used at SURFsara. Not having up to date packages for common Linux distributions was also problematic.
- As a result of writing the final SD report it was found that access via HTTP is possible via the CDMI protocol. There are plans to try this out in the future and would like to suggest mentioning this in the Onedata user documentation. It is currently 'hidden' in the "advanced usages" section, while it is considered that downloading a file a basic usage of the system.
- In general, the lack of a coherent set of high-level services meant that the SD had to build the entire demonstrator from the VM-level up.

Recommendations:

- EOSC is in need of a coherent set of high-level services aimed at researchers. The current set of services are too disjoint to be useful. Some prime examples of services we would like to see:
 - File sharing (Dropbox for large data sets).
 - Execution services for standards-based workflows.
 - Authentication and Authorization services.
 - Persistent storage (with identifiers like DOIs).

Political challenges & recommendations:

- In general, it was hard getting our input datasets into a FAIR state. As these were not created by us, attempts to make these FAIR led to nothing.

⁶² <https://www.ewatercycle.org>

- Most of the input dataset required for the SD research are not open data, making it impossible to build open science upon them.

Recommendations:

- The EOSC should actively engage dataset providers for creating a FAIR version of each dataset. Individual researchers are often unable to do this themselves, mostly due to lack of time.
- Creating Open, not only FAIR, datasets should be one of the goals of the EOSC.
- The EOSC should focus more on creating a community of users and providers, including intermediate roles such as RSEs and Data Stewards.

Interoperability issues:

- It would have helped greatly if support for services such as OneData was present on a number of computing facilities. As it stands now, the integration of services seems to all be up to the user of the EOSC.

3.3.5. VisualMedia: a service for sharing and visualizing visual media files on the web

The VisualMedia service provides researchers with a system to publish on the web, visualize and analyze images and 3D models in a common workspace, enabling sharing, interoperability and reuse. It supports:

- Web publications and visualization of high-resolution images and 3D models.
- Thumbnail-based browsing interface.
- Automatic conversion of data files into formats supporting efficient web-based publication, transmission and visualization.

The technical objectives followed during the EOSCpilot project were:

- Customization of presentation through the selection of different browsing systems for 3D models.
- Porting Visual Media Service onto a cloud platform with more sophisticated support for a number of issues (user authentication, control of the allocation/use of computing and storage resources in real time).
- Visual (2D and 3D) data visualization improvements.
- An increase in collaborative research.
- To educate Cultural Heritage (CH) researchers in moving towards the incorporation of virtual research environments in research methodology and to experience the use of cooperative visualization.

The CNR team collaborated with EOSCpilot staff in order to run the workflow under the D4Science Infrastructure, an activity that involved three steps:

- Authentication - adding authentication - incorporated the authentication feature of D4Science, including support of the D4Science and the Google authentication features.
- Storage - personal storage management - implemented a few small services connected with the now available user data.
- Evaluate scalability issues.

The main technical achievements during the project are:

- The SD managed to incorporate the authentication feature of D4Science. Authentication included support of: D4Science authentication, Google authentication and a password-less login option (based on email). Managing the authentication was not just incorporating the initial login and authentication dialog; it also required several changes to the internal organization of the Visual Media Service and its functionalities/interfaces (e.g. possibility of presenting visually only the data owned by a specific user, notifications about the job status through the D4Science 'social' system).

- In addition, several changes were introduced to the code of the Visual Media Server. Among these are the following:
 - The internal 3D browsing visualizer has been updated with the last version of the Nexus data conversion and rendering engine;
 - The format adopted to manage RTI data was changed, incorporating the new Relight format⁶³ recently proposed by CNR-ISTI (published at Web3D 2018 Conf. in last June). This new format enables better data encoding (improved space/quality ratio), a standard multi-resolution format based on image pyramids (following the Google maps approach), is compatible with DeepZoom⁶⁴ and Zoomify⁶⁵ formats, supports IIP⁶⁶ and IIIF⁶⁷ for interoperability;
 - Introduced the automatic production of thumbnails and use them in the visualization interface and in the browsing interface;
 - Added an option to support the online configuration of the visualization tools.
- User testing activities were undertaken between September and October 2018. The SD asked selected users to upload new data material and to test the revised and extended service. This activity progressed quite well, with many new datasets uploaded by users and several bug notifications made - which were promptly corrected. The overall evaluation of the users was very good.

Technical challenges:

- Supporting and enhancing the availability of FAIR data is a key issue in many scientific domains. The Visual Media Service tries to propose a solution to some key issues: how to manage the multiplicity of visual data types, the many visualization applications available/needed for each data type, the complexity of publishing those data on the web to allow easier sharing between experts. Instead of working at the data standardization level, it was decided to work at the data tools level – i.e. offer a single generic tool to allow the community to share and visualize visual data on the web.

Political challenges:

- The main political challenge in the Cultural Heritage domain is to convince potential users of the added-value of uploading visual media results and to make them available to the community on the web. Visual Media Service has been mainly designed for the Cultural Heritage community. Many people in this community are still very protective of the data they produce or are working with. The goal is therefore to convince them that the added-value of sharing the data with ‘remote’ colleagues is more important than the possible risk of losing unique access over the data or to lose control of the data.
- Mitigation:
 - There is no reward or incentive to increase the quantity (and quality) of the data being shared. In many disciplines visual data are a basic and critical resource in the scientific process, and Cultural Heritage is a good example of this. There needs to be incentives to foster data sharing. For example, considering quantity and quality of data shared as one of the items evaluated in the promotion or hiring process.

Cultural challenges:

- Standard e-infrastructure is often too much oriented to ICT developers (offering basic technologies). If we consider the specific Cultural Heritage domain/community, then most of the potential users

⁶³ <http://vcg.isti.cnr.it/relight/>

⁶⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Deep_Zoom

⁶⁵ <http://www.zoomify.com/>

⁶⁶ <https://iipimage.sourceforge.io/documentation/protocol/>

⁶⁷ <https://iiif.io/>

are looking for ‘ready to use’ solutions/tools rather than libraries to be used for software development.

- Mitigation:
 - Increase the number of tools or services built on top of basic infrastructure resource.

Interoperability challenges:

- There were taken into consideration some interoperability issues related to the visual data accessibility through different tools/architectures/web services. Concerning the easier case (2D images) it was followed the approach proposed by IFFF (International Image Interoperability Framework⁶⁸).

Figure 10 presents the summary of the results of the Interoperability Quick Assessment Questionnaire for the VisualMedia solution.

Figure 10: VisualMedia Potential Interoperability Score

⁶⁸ <https://iif.io>

4. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable represents the last deliverable of WP6. It aims to provide not only the final status of the different testbeds used by the demonstrators involved in the EOSCpilot project, but also the outcomes of the activities done, with a particular focus on the interoperability aspects of the solutions used or developed during the project and of infrastructures. Also, suggestions and recommendations that emerge from these activities, and contribute to improving the EOSC environment.

We also present the initial results of a self-assessment interoperability questionnaire that leverages one of the outcomes of the ISA² programme, Action 2016.36⁶⁹, “Assessment of trans-European systems supporting EU policies of the Interoperability solutions and common frameworks” – the **Interoperability Quick Assessment Toolkit (IQAT®)**⁷⁰. The IQAT’s objective is to allow Solution Owners to assess the Potential Interoperability of their software solutions supporting Public Services. In particular, we used the **Interoperability Quick Assessment Excel Tool**, an Excel tool used to calculate solutions interoperability maturity, and the **Guidelines for Solution Owners**, a short document that includes the **methodology** that describes the high-level steps **to be followed by Solution Owners for assessing the potential interoperability** of a solution. The results collected show fair and very good scores for the majority of the solutions that answered the questionnaire.

Some of the solutions, both at the level of services used and solutions implemented by the Science Demonstrator are already included in the EOSC environment, and are part of the EOSC Portal marketplace, confirming their quality and high readiness levels:

- PROMINENCE, Enabling HTC & HPC applications opportunistically across private, academic and public clouds:
<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/prominence>
- PaN Data, dCache backend storage for the EOSC PaN Science Demonstrator:
<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/pan-data>
- PaN FaaS, OpenWhisk, cloud functions for the EOSC PAN Science Demonstrator:
<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/pan-faas>
- PaN Notebook, Spawn Jupyter Servers in the DESY Compute Cloud and run notebooks which can make use of the EOSC PaN FaaS Service and connect to EOSC PaN Data Service:
<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/pan-notebook>
- B2SHARE, Store and publish research data:
<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/b2share>
- DODAS, Simplify the access and management of computing resources:
<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/dynamic-on-demand-analysis-service-dodas-portal>

While others are indirectly used by the above, and/or under evaluation to be included in the marketplace as separate services like INDIGO IAM, PaaS Orchestrator, udocker, Onedata.

⁶⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/actions/evaluating-and-rationalising-ict-public-administrations_en

⁷⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/solutions/interoperability-quick-assessment-toolkit-iqat_en

ANNEX 1. GLOSSARY

Many definitions are taken from the EGI Glossary (<https://wiki.egi.eu/wiki/Glossary>). They are indicated by (EGI definition).

Term	Explanation
e-infrastructures	(Definition of the Commission High Level Expert Group on the European Open Science Cloud in their report): this term is used to refer in a broader sense to all ICT-related infrastructures supporting ESFRIS (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures) or research consortia or individual research groups, regardless of whether they are funded under the CONNECT scheme, nationally or locally.
High Performance Computing (HPC)	(EGI definition) A computing paradigm that focuses on the efficient execution of compute intensive, tightly-coupled tasks. Given the high parallel communication requirements, the tasks are typically executed on low latency interconnects which makes it possible to share data very rapidly between a large number of processors working on the same problem. HPC systems are delivered through low latency clusters and supercomputers and are typically optimized to maximize the number of operations per seconds. The typical metrics are FLOPS, tasks/s, I/O rates.
High Throughput Computing (HTC)	(EGI definition) A computing paradigm that focuses on the efficient execution of a large number of loosely-coupled tasks. Given the minimal parallel communication requirements, the tasks can be executed on clusters or physically distributed resources using grid technologies. HTC systems are typically optimized to maximize the throughput over a long period of time and a typical metric is jobs per month or year.

Term	Explanation
National Grid Initiative or National Grid Infrastructure (NGI)	(EGI definition) The national federation of shared computing, storage and data resources that delivers sustainable, integrated and secure distributed computing services to the national research communities and their international collaborators. The federation is coordinated by a National Coordinating Body providing a single point of contact at the national level and has official membership in the EGI Council through an NGI legal representative .
Virtual Organization (VO)	A group of people (e.g. scientists, researchers) with common interests and requirements, who need to work collaboratively and/or share resources (e.g. data, software, expertise, CPU, storage space) regardless of geographical location. They join a VO in order to access resources to meet these needs, after agreeing to a set of rules and Policies that govern their access and security rights (to users, resources and data).
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
CMS	Content Management System
EDMI	EOSC Dataset Minimum Information
EOSC	The European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RIs	Research infrastructures

ANNEX 2. INTEROPERABILTY QUICK ASSESSMENT TOOL

This annex presents the Interoperability Quick Assessment Tool, an Excel application used to calculate solutions interoperability maturity. This was used to assess the interoperability potential of the various software solutions used/improved/developed by the Science Demonstrators during the lifetime of the EOSCpilot project.

The version presented has been converted to static PDF.

European Commission - ISA Unit Interoperability Quick Assessment Tool

Tool Release Date: 14/02/2018

Tool Version: 1.1.0

Start >

For any request related to this Interoperability Assessment tool, please send an email by clicking on this button:

Send an email >

Interoperability Quick Assessment Tool

Fill the questionnaire to quickly assess the Interoperability level of your solution.

Navigation

Quick Guidelines

IOP Governance

- Click on any area of the IOP Assessment Conceptual Model to jump to the questionnaire section of the IOP Area

Software Architecture

H2M Interface

To select the answer click the ✓ option from the drop-down list; To unselect click the "blank" option (or press "canc" on the keyboard)

M2M Interface

Click on the "! More Info" cells to show additional information

Please, fill in the requested information about your solution.

All the answers required.

Answer

Solution official name	
Solution Provider	
Solution Owner	
Informant (who provided the info for the IOP Assessment)	
Date of the Interoperability Assessment	

IOP GOVERNANCE

G1

Interoperability by Design

For each statement, please indicate whether the statement was considered during the design or procurement phase of your solution.

Please reply to each of the following statements.

		Considered and applied	Considered and partially applied	Not considered	Considered and found to be not relevant
1	When designing the solution, preference was given to open interoperability specifications	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	When designing the solution, the effectiveness and efficiency of different solutions considering user-needs, proportionality and balance between costs and benefits were evaluated	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	When designing the solution, coherence with the relevant legislation has been evaluated	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	When designing the solution, mechanisms for co-creating and involving the users were put in place	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

5	When procuring or designing the solution, a structured, transparent, objective and common approach in assessing and selecting standards and specifications was used. EU recommendations, in this respect, were taken into account and coherence for these approaches across borders was achieved	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	Security is taken into account at design phase	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

G2 Interoperability Strategies and Plans

Please, indicate whether the following IOP strategies and plans have been considered and applied during the operation of your solution.

Please reply to each of the following statements.

		Considered and applied	Considered and partially applied	Not considered	Considered and found to be not relevant
1	Interoperability strategy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Long-term preservation policy for information (especially for information that is exchanged across borders)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Data quality assurance plans for base registries and related master data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Security and privacy strategies (or recommendations, guidelines, etc.) to ensure secure data exchange	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Interoperability agreements (Interoperability Service Agreements, Interoperability Collaboration Agreements or Interoperability Provider Agreements)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	Information management strategy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7	Other IOP-related strategy/plan (please name below):	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

G3 Processes enabling Interoperability

Please indicate whether the following processes enabling IoP were considered and applied to support the operation of your solution.

Please reply to each of the following statements.

Considered and applied
Considered and partially applied
Not considered
Considered and found to be not relevant

1	Procedures to constantly simplify processes and use digital channels whenever appropriate for the delivery of your solution, to respond timely and with high quality to users' requests and reduce the administrative burden imposed on administrations, businesses and citizens	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Processes for data and information management lifecycle (collection/generation, protection, preservation, sharing)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Processes to integrate the opening of data in common business processes and working routines, and also when developing new information systems	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Change management processes to ensure continuous service delivery	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Processes to select relevant standards and specifications, evaluate them, monitor their implementation, check compliance and test their interoperability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	Processes to enable co-creation and involvement of users in the assessment and evolution of the solution	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7	Processes to document your business processes using commonly accepted modelling techniques and agree on how these processes will interact to deliver the solution	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE

A1 Architectural Maturity: Solution Building Blocks

Which of the EIRA Solution Building Blocks (SBB) are included in the solution and which is the maturity level of each of them?

Please reply to each of the following statements.

Please, click on the "Component" or "Service" cell to show the EIRA v2 definition of each of the following EIRA building blocks.

The following list of building blocks is based on EIRA v2 (Technical - Application View and Technical - Infrastructure View).

		Monolithic piece of code	Component	Service	ABB not implemented / not needed
1	Application (Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Business Intelligence (Component)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Business Analytics (Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Business Reporting (Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Data Transformation (Component or Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	Data Validation (Component or Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7	Access Management (Component or Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8	Audit and Logging (Component)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

9	Audit (Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
10	Logging (Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
11	Test (Component or Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
12	Business Process Management (Component)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
13	Choreography (Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
14	Orchestration (Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
15	Service Discovery (Component or Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
16	Configuration and Cartography (Component or Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
17	Collaboration (Component)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
18	Audiovisual (Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
19	Messaging (Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
20	Service Registry Component / Service Registration Service	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
21	e-Payment (Component or Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
22	Administration (Component)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
23	Administration and monitoring (Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
24	Lifecycle Management (Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
25	Partner Management (Component or Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
26	Content Management (Component or Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
27	Document Management (Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
28	e-Archiving (Component or Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
29	Data Publication (Component or Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
30	Forms Management (Component or Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
31	Metadata Management (Component or Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
32	Record Management (Component or Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

33	Data Exchange (Component or Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
34	Identity Management (Component or Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
35	Trust Service Provisioning (Component)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
36	e-Seal Creation (Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
37	e-Seal Preservation (Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
38	e-Seal Verification and Validation (Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
39	e-Signature Creation (Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
40	e-Signature Preservation (Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
41	e-Signature Verification and Validation (Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
42	e-Timestamp Creation (Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
43	e-Timestamp Verification and Validation (Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
44	Registered Electronic Delivery (Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
45	Trust Registry (Component or Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
46	Machine Translation (Component or Service)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

A2 Architectural Maturity: Business Processes Orchestration

Is a Business Process Management Component included in your solution and are mature standards used?

Answer

Only one answer.

1	Yes, the solution has a Business Process Management Component and business processes are configured and executed using mature standards (e.g. BPMN 2.0, WS-BPEL)	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Yes, the solution has a Business Process Management Component but business processes are configured and executed using proprietary standards	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	No, the solution does not include a Business Process Management Component	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Not applicable, as the solution does not need to configure and execute business processes	<input type="checkbox"/>

A3 Availability: Service Registration Service

Are Solution services registered through a Service Registration Service within a catalogue to be discovered by other services?

Answer

Only one answer.

1	Yes, all solution's services are registered through a Service Registration Service	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Partly, only some of solution's services are registered through a Service Registration Service	<input type="checkbox"/>

3	No, no solution service is registered through a Service Registration Service	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Not applicable, the solution does not have any service that can / should be published through a Service Registration Service	<input type="checkbox"/>

A4 IOP Test Services / Scenarios

Does the solution provide Test Services and Test Scenarios for Interoperability?

Answer

Only one answer.

1	Yes, the solution provides Test Scenarios and Test Services for Interoperability, uses a Service Registration Service to register the Test Services in a catalogue and hosts Test Scenarios in a public repository	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Yes, the solution only provides Test Scenarios and Test Services for Interoperability	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Yes, the solution only provides Test Scenarios for Interoperability	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	No, the solution does not provide Test Scenarios nor Test Services	<input type="checkbox"/>

A5 Solution Documentation

Is your solution supported by relevant documentation?

Is there such a documentation?
If so, is it available in digital form?

Several answers possible. Availability of documentation is required to check also the digital availability.

1	Configuration Management	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Data Models	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Operational Procedures	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Technical Specifications	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Test Scenarios	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	Test Reports	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

HUMAN-TO-MACHINE INTERFACE

H1 User-Centricity: Multi-Channel Delivery

Please, indicate through which delivery channels your solution is made available to its direct (human) users.

Answer

Several answers possible.

1	Website / Web App	<input type="checkbox"/>
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2	Portal (functionality that is directly accessible on a portal, via a Portlet, together with related information from various sources)	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Dedicated application (functionality that requires software installation on a device by the end user. This includes apps from an online application store)	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Telephone (e.g. IVR system)	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Not applicable, the solution doesn't have Human Interfaces	<input type="checkbox"/>

H2 User-Centricity: Device / Platform / Browser Independency

Does your solution support multiple devices, platforms or browsers? Answer

Select the option best describing the solution.

1	Yes, the solution supports all major devices, platforms and/or browsers	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Partly, the solution supports multiple but not all major devices, platform and/or browsers	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	No, the solution supports only a single device, platform and/or browser	<input type="checkbox"/>

H3 Accessibility: e-Accessibility Specifications

Is your solution accessible according to relevant e-accessibility specifications? Answer

Select the option best describing the solution.

1	Yes, in full (maximum conformance level - e.g. AAA or AA in ISO/IEC 40500:2012)	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Partly (non-maximum conformance level - e.g. A in ISO/IEC 40500:2012)	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	No, the solution doesn't comply with any e-accessibility specification widely recognised at European or International Level	<input type="checkbox"/>

H4 Accessibility: Multilingualism

To what extent is multilingualism supported by the solution? Answer

Select the option best describing the solution.

1	Fully, the entire solution (user interface, support documentation, technical specifications, etc.) is multilingual, and all translations are performed through a machine translation component or service (e.g. EC Translation Machine)	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Fully, the entire solution (user interface, support documentation, technical specifications, etc.) as such is multilingual, and all translations are performed manually	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Partly, only the user interface is multilingual	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Not at all, the user interface is provided only in one language, although users speak more than one language	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Not applicable, as this is not needed (users speak only one language)	<input type="checkbox"/>

H5 Open Data

Does your solution publish its data as open data, and in which format? Answer

Select the option best describing the solution.

1	Yes, as linked open data	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Yes, in non-proprietary formats with semantic metadata / ontologies (e.g. rdf)	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Yes, in structured, non-proprietary formats (e.g. csv, json)	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Yes, in structured, proprietary formats (e.g. MS Excel)	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Yes, in non-structured formats (e.g. pdf, jpeg)	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	No, the solution does not publish open data, while it could	<input type="checkbox"/>
7	Not applicable, open data are not relevant for the solution	<input type="checkbox"/>

MACHINE-TO-MACHINE INTERFACE

M1 Data Exchange

Does your solution exchange information and data with other ICT systems?

Answer

Only one answer.

1	Yes, all data are transferred automatically	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Yes, data are transferred both automatically and manually	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Yes, data are transferred only manually	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	No, although it could exchange data	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Not applicable, exchanging information and data is not relevant for this solution	<input type="checkbox"/>

M2 Data Exchange: Interaction Type

Are data exchange interactions between your solution and other ICT systems mostly synchronous or asynchronous? In the case of asynchronous interactions, are they implemented using batch or event processing?

Answer

Only one answer.

1	Mostly through synchronous interactions (e.g. through web services)	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Mostly through asynchronous interactions with batch processing (e.g. ETL scheduled jobs)	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Mostly through asynchronous interactions with event processing (e.g. asynchronous messaging)	<input type="checkbox"/>

M3 Data Exchange: Transfer Channel

Through which channel, prevalently, does your solution exchange data with other ICT systems?

Answer

Only one answer.

1	Mostly through web services (REST, SOAP, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Mostly through file transfer (exchange of flat files, documents, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>

3	Mostly through database interconnections (database links, database views, etc.)	
---	---	--

M4 Data Exchange: Data Format

Which is the prevalent data format your solution uses to exchange data with other ICT systems?

Answer

Only one answer.

1	Mostly self-describing, structured data format (e.g. XML, JSON, SGML, etc.)	
2	Mostly flat, structured data format (e.g. csv, flat text, etc.)	
3	Mostly unstructured data format (i.e. blob / text)	

IOP Final Scores

Solution official name	
Solution Provider	
Solution Owner	
Informant	
Date of the Interoperability Assessment	

	Weight	Sub-total	IOP Area score	Maturity Level
IOP GOVERNANCE	30.0	0.0	0.0%	<i>This IOP Area has been assessed to have Poor Interoperability. This solution performed poor in the IOP Area and the potential interoperability is considered as having substantial room for improvement.</i>
SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE	40.0	0.0	0.0%	<i>This IOP Area has been assessed to have Poor Interoperability. This solution performed poor in the IOP Area and the potential interoperability is considered as having substantial room for improvement.</i>
HUMAN-TO-MACHINE INTERFACE	10.0	0.0	0.0%	<i>This IOP Area has been assessed to have Poor Interoperability. This solution performed poor in the IOP Area and the potential interoperability is considered as having substantial room for improvement.</i>
MACHINE-TO-MACHINE INTERFACE	20.0	0.0	0.0%	<i>This IOP Area has been assessed to have Poor Interoperability. This solution performed poor in the IOP Area and the potential interoperability is considered as having substantial room for improvement.</i>
SOLUTION TOTAL IOP SCORE		0.0		

This solution has been assessed to have Poor Interoperability. This solution, on average, performed poor in the relevant criteria and the potential interoperability of this solution is considered as having substantial room for improvement.

